

Master Thesis in Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Exploring Objectivity in the Aesthetic Experience of Audio Quality

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Supervisor: Perfecto Herrera-Boyer

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Abstract

In this thesis we present the results of research into the effects of the technological mediation of music on the aesthetic experience as an attempt to reconcile the difference between the humanities and computational approaches to aesthetics. Both traditions believe they are measuring the value of ‘a work of art’. However it has not been considered that they may be measuring different things; one is evaluating the work, as an abstract conceptualisation, the other as the stimuli actually received by the listener. Exploring the space between these two hopes not only to alloy the two camps, but also posits an interesting space in which to gain insight on the aesthetic experience.

We tackled this by degrading compositions through audio transformation, and presenting these to be ranked by participants. Using this information, we explored the relationships between the rankings and an array of statistical descriptors extracted from the transformed audio using Essentia’s Music Extractor.

The questionnaire pointed towards a clear trend in aesthetic judgments made by our subjects. The degradations that were most preferred were the most associated with a technological mediation, such as telephone, radio (Band-pass filtering) or an arguably overused audio tool (Audio Compression). In contrasted those least preferred were more associated with human performance error, such as mistuning (Harmonic Randomisation) and mis-timing (Transient Removal).

The most highly correlated Essentia descriptors referred to *spectral*, *loudness* and *tonal* qualities of the signal. It was also found that the Normalised Compression Distance between each version and its original reference version was the most highly correlated descriptor.

Our findings suggest that there is in fact a degree of objectivity in the way we make aesthetic judgements of audio at the ‘micro-level’. The results of the correlation coefficients between the NCD and the rankings contribute to the compression progress theory of aesthetic value promoted by authors such as Machado and Cardoso[1]

and Schmidhuber[2]. Our findings should inform the methods of any research that aims to measure the aesthetic value of different compositions relative to one another. The stimuli presented are not abstract representations of ‘a composition’, but rather versions of ‘a composition’ where ‘non-artistic’ interventions will factor in on the aesthetic experience they induce.

Keywords: Computational aesthetics; Empirical aesthetics; Music perception

Chapter 1

Introduction

The proselytisation of machine learning has preached its endless applicability; the idea that all phenomenon will be explicable with enough data and enough computational power professes to have no limitation. The inevitable conclusion of this has been the development of ‘computational aesthetics’, the data-driven mode of enquiry that is concerned with the computational assessment of beauty in the domains of human creative expression. The goals of this practice are wide-ranging, from measuring the aesthetic value of individual works of art and understanding the neural processing that produces the aesthetic experience, to developing generative art and AI artists.

We have found that certain music or audio specific considerations have not been taken into account. Some of the current ambitions of the computational aesthetics of music- most notably measuring the aesthetic value of compositions relative to one another- require a more incremental approach. For instance, the effects of technological mediation on the abstract conceptualisation of ‘the composition’ have not been considered.

‘A composition’ is realised in a unique environment almost every time it is listened to; a new performance, a streamed version instead of vinyl playback, a different hifi, a different room, a change in air temperature. Some of these are sweeping alterations, some of these are minute, but they all affect the aesthetic experience of

the listener. This is the difference between the ‘work’, an abstract conceptualisation, and the ‘object’, the stimuli actually received by the listener.

The goal of this research is therefore to explore the relationship between the aesthetic experience and the smallest aesthetic decisions, decisions which are beyond what is traditionally considered to be ‘artistic’. In other words, we believe that before we can successfully measure the value of whole compositions in relation to one another, we need to evaluate the different ways in which compositions are often presented. It is our hypothesis that this is the most likely place to find objectivity in the aesthetic experience because we are here examining the effects of the smallest of aesthetic decisions. Furthermore, our assertions should scale up.

Our methods, outlined in Chapter 4, look at degrading compositions through transformations, and presenting these to be ranked by participants. Using this information we explore the relationships between the rankings and an array of statistical descriptors extracted from transformed audio.

We will present a highly condensed overview of the development of aesthetic thought in Chapter 2, from a historical and philosophical perspective and the ‘scientific’, latterly computational, approaches to the study of aesthetics, closing with a discussion regarding the most compelling computational theories. This is followed by a discussion in greater detail on the problem area tackled by this research, some a priori assumptions, and the theoretical framework that this work finds itself in. After detailing our methods in Chapter 4, Chapter 5 will present our results with a discussion of both the novel approach and its relation to the theories commented on earlier in the thesis.

Chapter 2

State of The Art

This chapter will provide a highly condensed overview of a field of human intellectual engagement that has spanned several millennia. It will alloy both the humanities and ‘scientific’, latterly computational, approaches to the study aesthetic, commenting on where they intersect and deviate. We will begin with some historical context, tracing the roots of the tradition of aesthetic enquiry from Ancient India, through the enlightenment thinks, and finally to the 20th-century discourse and fracturing of approaches. Following this, contemporary empirical methods are discussed that will include work from a variety of disciplines such as evolutionary biology, brain imaging, neuropsychology, neuroaesthetics and information theory. The chapter will close with a summary of what we will take forward into the following chapter that will refine the task ahead.

2.1 Historical Perspective

2.1.1 Antiquity

The majority of condensed summaries on the development of aesthetic enquiry tend to start in ancient Athens, but the ancient Greeks were by no means the first to consider such a phenomenon. To the best of our knowledge, the study goes at least as far back as the Vedic era texts in ancient India. The Aitareya Brahmana, (1000

BCE) suggests that the arts are for a refinement of the self. Following this, the aesthetic experience would come to be defined in these works as ‘Rasa’, roughly translating to something close to ‘flavour’ in English, but more broadly referring to the invocation of an emotion that “can not be explained”.

The discussion of aesthetics that lies latent in pre-Socratic Greek philosophy is, however, the first to consider an arithmetical account of aesthetics. Pythagoras, Plato, and Aristotle worked on quantitative expressions of proportion and beauty.

Pythagoreans, for instance, quantified ‘harmonious’ musical intervals in terms of proportions (ratios) of the first few whole numbers: a unison is 1:1, an octave is 2:1, perfect fifth is 3:2, perfect fourth is 4:3, etc.

Plato’s theory of forms postulates that incorporeal, unchanging, ideal paradigms - i.e. forms - are universal. For Plato ‘Beauty’ (which we should take to be precedent to, and synonymous with, ‘aesthetic’), is, as many other properties are, provoked by its respective form. We can see mention of Beauty (the Form) as the cause of beauty (property) throughout Plato’s middle to late writing; see *Cratylus* 439C-440B, *Phaedrus* 254B, *Phaedo* 65d-66A etc. It is also suggested, that there appears to be a connection between Beauty (the Form) and Good (the Form).

The form is everlasting, not beautiful under some circumstances or in any specific condition. The idea of the form (though always with a small ‘f’) will continue to crop up at different points throughout aesthetic thinking.

Critical of Plato’s theory of the forms, Aristotle outlines several principles and universal elements or qualities that are that are crucial and present in any beautiful object, such as symmetry and definiteness. In the *Poetics* he specifies a relation, of magnitude (size) to clearness of perception(1450B). As we’ll soon see, ideas related to complexity and perception will become incredibly relevant to the contemporary discussions on computation aesthetics.

For Aristotle (indeed Plato also) a discussion of the arts and of beauty was not complete if it did not make mention of *mimesis*. *Mimesis*, or mimicry, is said

to be the natural method of learning from childhood and a “source of delight for human beings”. Aristotle utilises this when considering the experience of looking at a painting. One may delight in the recognition of the specifics of a depiction for it allows them to ‘gather the meaning of things’. But they may also find pleasure elsewhere; admiration of the execution, of the use of colour and shape and so on. The later here is very similar to a contemporary ‘empirical’ conception of aesthetics. For Aristotle both are necessary for the enrichment of the viewer; colour and figures are not meant to be imitations but symbols (1340A). We will see the relevance (or necessity) of symbolism in aesthetics being challenged in later discourse.

Developments in (Western) aesthetic thinking between the Greeks and the Enlightenment were largely the domain of the church, Romain Catholic and Orthodox. Worthy of note here would be the contribution of Saint Thomas Aquinas who went some way to bridge the gap between ‘the object’ and ‘the perception’- “beauty is that which gives pleasure when seen”. It will become clear in the later discussion on the difference between ‘aesthetic value’ and the ‘aesthetic experience’.

For Aquinas, knowledge, which is key to his conception of beauty, occurs when the form of an object, abstract of its matter, exists in the mind of the perceiver. We can easily draw parallels here between Plato’s theory of form, in that knowledge of the form proceeds beauty, but here the focus is shifted squarely towards the percept[3]. More generally, however, it could be argued that both of their characterisations is inceptive of the, yet unimagined, idea of neural encoding.

From antiquity through the middle ages we see that the idea of beauty remains elusive and intangible but its relation to geometry, space and form is undisputed. This provokes much discussion on the mind’s processing of such, beyond simply the recognition of talent or skill.

2.1.2 Post-Enlightenment

Aesthetics took on a more familiar discursive form with the work of Alexander Baumgarten. It is in his work of 1750, *Aesthetica*[4], he is said to have coined

the term. His derivation drew from the Greek for “senses”, as for him beauty was considered perfect ‘sense-knowledge’, and thus the study of it was a study of ‘sensible cognition’.

David Hume’s ‘The Standard of Taste’[5] is the first time we see a consideration of the possibility of beauty’s relativity. Here, he questions the epistemology of an aesthetic theory that includes subjectivity; if beauty is a perception, or a judgement, rather than a characteristic of the object, then how can we understand the possibility of some truth or a standard of judgement. In ‘The Treatise’, he writes “pleasure and pain [...] are not only necessary attendants of beauty and deformity but constitute their very essence”. Hume makes no distinction between aesthetic value and the aesthetic experience, or that in the very least the aesthetic value is simply defined by the aesthetic experience.

Kant follows both Hume and Baumgarten, but before discussing his thinking it is worthy to note, however, that Kant proposes a significant expansion of the term’s remit. Kant considers all sensual experience aesthetic; his definition logically implies that even the sight of an idea expressed numerically to be an aesthetic experience. Arguably this would not be considered an aesthetic experience under a contemporary definition, but as we’ll see later (in Section 2.5) it is argued that these pleasures come from the same neurologic well-spring.

Kant tackles the issue of a normative aesthetic judgment directly, following the empiricists in taking the perception of taste to be found in personal feelings of pleasure, and thus subjective. However, for Kant, aesthetic judgements are like (though separate from) cognitive ones, in that they appear to lay claim to universal agreement (when one judges something to be beautiful, it is a natural inclination to believe that it is also beautiful to everyone else, even though we lack the ability to prove so).

He argues that a ‘harmony of the faculties of the imagination and the understanding’ gives rise to pleasurable sensations. This, in turn, is caused by ‘free play’ in the process of cognising objects on the basis of empirical discernment. We will later

see the parallels to this sort of thinking in contemporary neuroaesthetic findings (see Section 2.4). Fascinatingly, Kant was quite correct in supposing the work of encoding an aesthetic percept would be split between specific brain modules, and that a harmony of activity in these regions would correlate with a pleasurable response (see Section 2.7). The ‘freedom’ of this harmony is found in the fact that it is not forced by rules of understanding, unlike acts of cognition, this, for Kant gives it its essential subjectivity[6].

This is where Kant limits his applicability to computational or empirical aesthetics, as for him, an aesthetic judgment is distinctly an ‘individual one’, absent of the notion of a universal judgement of features i.e “all objects possessing such and such qualities are beautiful” suggesting a judgement of that form would be a logical one, which for Kant was distinct from an aesthetic one[7]. By reading this exclusively one could be lead to believe that any work of computational aesthetics that deals directly with relating features of the object with a universal experience is in its nature anti-Kantian, but this reveals a contradiction in Kant’s work, in that surely “all objects that posses [or cause]” a “harmony of the faculties of the imagination and the understanding” upon viewing are beautiful?

Enlightenment thinkers expand the idea that cognising objects and symbols is central to the aesthetic experience, but they open up a new rift in the ways of thinking about this phenomenon. The debate over subjectivity and objectivity in the personal derivation of pleasure from beauty is matched with a discussion on the properties of the subject and the object. Kant foreshadows the idea that the basic building blocks of cognition used in harmonious ways produce the aesthetic experience, and Herbert suggests the basic building blocks of composition hold no aesthetic value of their own but must be used in harmonious ways to create aesthetic value.

J.F. Herbert, a neo-Kantian who adopted the view of aesthetic judgment as singular, or individual, finds a method of adding a certain degree of logical universality to the subjectivity argument by emphasising that the predicate (beauty) is always true of the same aesthetic object. In other words, that universality is shown by the fact that what is at once perceived to be beautiful remains so; even if we were to tire at

looking at or listening to an aesthetic object, we would not consider them to have degraded in beauty. Herbert here also carefully delineates the beautiful from the useful or the pleasant; time, place, person and context affect the latter two but not the aesthetic.

Herbert also addresses the idea of elemental composition in aesthetics and in doing so addresses music directly, suggesting, in a treatise that soon became the manifesto for the formalist tradition, that “no single tone can be considered, in itself, beautiful or ugly, [...] single tones constitute the intervals and chords that, as relations, elicit aesthetic judgment”[8]. This thinking is both reminiscent of Platonic Forms but also touches on several other ideas that will be referenced later in this chapter, such as Bell’s ‘significant form’[9] and the Gestalt principals of psychology (see Section 2.3).

Another thinker from the turn of the 20th Century whose writing is worthy of mention would be Eduard Hanslick, a critic and a personal acquaintance of Johannes Brahms, whose contributions to the debate that commanded the discourse of the music intelligentsia at the time are also pertinent to this discussion. The debate was over the capacity of music to express non-musical ideas. Those that believed that music could fundamentally express only musical ideas, took the “absolutist” viewpoint and it was for this position that Hanslick wrote. For Hanslick the Beauty in music follows not from forms but from logic or ‘laws’. These laws govern the relationship between the “human organism” and the “phenomena of sound”, and for Hanslick, an aesthetic experience would be the product of an ‘elemental composition’ in accordance with these laws.[10].

2.1.3 The 20th-Century Aesthetic Divide

Aesthetic theory in the 20th century diverged in separate trajectories: one of esotericism, becoming a largely abstruse, Hegelian, socio-political enquiry. In following this it becomes impossible to study aesthetics in isolation; aesthetics becomes bound to a theory or philosophy of art (see Adorno[11] of the Frankfurt School et al.). Hargreaves and North call the above approach ‘Speculative Aesthetics’[12], the other

is a more empirical study, one that's foundational to any work of computational aesthetics.

What separates 20th Century empirical enquiry from a simply logical one is the gift of the insights drawn in the previous era. The questions of the philosophy covered previously largely concern themselves with 'the what' and 'the where' of aesthetics. The former having covered much less ground than the later. The 'where' of aesthetics, especially if we draw from Kant, is 'the experience'. Accepting this allowed a narrowing of the search to a 'kind of experience' and for quasi-universality in the relationship of a common experience to objects. These qualifications over time move this trajectory of enquiry into the purview of psychologists, neuroscientists and evolutionary biologists.

Clive Bell was an early adopter of this tradition, considering aesthetic to be experiential. In his book simply titled 'Art'[9], Bell states that "aesthetics must be the personal experience of a peculiar emotion". This is the critique of Kant's position that was mentioned previously, for Bell any object that provokes this emotion in the viewer is definitively art.

In 'Aesthetic Measure'[13] Birkhoff organises the aesthetics objects implicit in the causation of the aesthetic experience into two categories. The first are found in nature: sunsets, hilltop vistas, the fractal patterns found in snowflakes etc, while the others are the work of artists. What Birkhoff finds to be common to both categories is the ratio between order and complexity, his focus being in the visual domain, he applies these principles to the value of several 2D contours. Birkhoff was also the first to present a formulaic analysis of aesthetic value:

$$aesthetic\ value = \frac{Order}{Complexity}$$

This expression of a relationship which is commonly known as the metaphor "unity in variety" harkens all the way back to the initial formalisations of the Ancient Greeks[14].

In *Art and Visual Perception*[15], Rudolf Arnheim proposed a Gestalt theory¹ of visual composition reliant on the interpretation of an image's centre of mass, the theory was later built upon in his later works[17, 18] and though it has proved influential since, especially to the works of Bense[19] and Staudek[20], it has recently been called into question by McManus et al.[21]

The 20th century saw the field split into, a largely sociocultural, aesthetic study, which relied heavily on the post-enlightenment philosophy and the traditional art criticism base, and a new empirical study. However, as we have seen this didn't end the inner dialect of the field; mutually exclusive studies of subject and object continued in empirical aesthetic discourse.

2.2 Evolutionary Biology, Adaptive Functions and Aesthetics

We tend to consider that ethology points towards a plausible explanation of how a given behaviour would be adaptive, and there is literature arguing that music had some sort of survival value [22] or that it may have had a hand in sexual selection [23], but dismissive arguments come from non-adaptive models like Pinker's [24]. These models, whilst gaining more popularity than adaptive ones have been notably disparaging of the role that music plays within humans' conscious experience (see metaphors like "auditory cheesecake").

Other approaches such as Hudson's[25] posit that an appreciation of music is the broader application of a more obviously adaptive tool. The recall of information and the processing of previous events leads to better decision making in the present. Unable to store the entirety of a lifetime of sensory input, the obvious adaptive solution to this problem is information compression, to formulate what is logical and what is novel, and store that in a more compact form than its native input. The relevance of this theory to a computation model is likely already evident but

¹Gestalt theory is an attempt to understand the laws behind our ability to acquire and maintain meaningful perception. The central tenet of Gestalt psychology is that the mind forms a global whole with self-organising tendencies.[16]

will be explored in greater depth in Section 2.5.

For Rolls, emotions can be defined, operationally, as states elicited by ‘rewards’ and ‘punishers’[26]. Anything for which an animal will work would trigger a reward, and conversely, the stimuli for the opposite would be anything an animal would want to escape from. Rolls ties these directly to sound, by suggesting that aesthetic judgments, in this case, could be a byproduct of a crucial mechanism in determining if auditory stimuli are linked to a punisher or a reward, therefore begetting a selection mechanism in developing the most effective determination[27]. He offers the example of harmonicity vs. inharmonicity in the human voice: an angry human voice may contain non-linearities in the vocal cords due to over-exertion, these could cause greater inharmonicity in the spectral content than that of a calm voice, the result of developing a mechanism attuned to these discrepancies in the modern human would be a discernment for the tuning of a musical instrument. Sachs et al’s work in neural connectivity support this claim, attributing social-emotional communication through the auditory channel as the evolutionary basis for music making due to an aesthetic rewarding function in humans[28].

There seems to be no single winning argument regarding exactly how we came to have the experiences of aesthetic stimuli that we do, but it is generally accepted that it must be linked to survival values that can be present in music or music-like communicative devices used by humans, for we are fairly certain that aesthetic experience (as a general sensation) is universal amongst all humans.

2.3 Empirical Aesthetics and Psychology

Brattico et al. contributed a review of the literature surrounding the origins of the aesthetic experience and music[29]. They open their paper with a discussion of the naturally anecdotal, but almost universal, aesthetic response to music as the transversal of emotions via attributes of value (beauty, harmony, elegance), and their association with pleasurable or un-pleasurable emotions (for more of this see Sacks[30]). Further, that these responses are reflected in listeners’ autonomic and

central nervous systems and can thus be measured objectively with a polygraph, electroencephalogram (EEG), positron emission tomography (PET) or functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI).

The authors suggest that the origins of the aesthetic response have largely been investigated on two fronts. Firstly a neurocognitive approach aimed to further our understanding of how musical stimuli are able to elicit emotional responses that do not directly relate to the physical properties of the stimuli (see Peretz[31]). The other asks how the neurocognitive mechanisms necessary for the production and reception of music developed from an evolutionary biology perspective, tracing back the evolutionary roadmap and discovering the causal forces operating therein.

In their study into the classification of images, where subjects were asked to classify images as ‘art’ or not, Pelowski et al[32] proposed two modes of operation in coming to an aesthetic judgement. Firstly ‘canonical classifications’, the use of cultural subtext or clues to almost game the question. i.e. “does it look like other works of art I know?” or “is it in a gallery or museum”? With the assumption that all object that looks like works of art are themselves likely to be works of art, or, that if it resides in a museum or gallery then it must be a work of art. The second method was that of assessing ones ‘hedonic reaction’. This is the assessment of one’s emotional experience upon engagement with the object. Their result shows that the two are strongly correlated, in that what one deems to be ‘art’ one appreciates more. In other words, consciously engaging with an object as an art object increases the aesthetic experience. They rightly avoid an argument of causation but stress that a subjects willingness to engage with an aesthetic object is pivotal to the aesthetic experience.

Leder et al. propose an information processing model for the psychology of human attraction to art[33]. Their model is hierarchical and makes a distinction between the ‘Aesthetic Emotion’ and the ‘Aesthetic Judgement’. It delineates the function of such with the aim of “mastering” the object. The language used here is not arbitrary, though for the perceiver ‘mastery’ may more colloquially be thought of as ‘understanding’, their word choice leans into some of the adaptive evolutionary

theory mentioned earlier. For Leder, artistic stimuli present the perceiver with a challenge, one of comprehension and classification; how to decode the message and understand the context the message is placed. The whole process of mastery is the ‘aesthetic experience’, whereas the ‘aesthetic emotion’ is the appraisal of the affective state induced in walking through the challenge.

In their ten-year retrospective review, Leder et al.[34] more incisively delineate their approach from a purely formalist one. They quote Bell (mentioned above [9]) as an originator of this approach; Bell allies the aesthetic emotion with visual (auditory or literal) form and the relations of forms. These forms are themselves derived from the encoding of sensory qualities such as complexity, order, proportion, colour combinations etc.

Hedonic value (a quality of the object), or ‘hedonic reaction’ (a quality of the subject) as used by Pelowski et al, was previously a focus of the work by Berlyne. Berlyne defines hedonic value as a value obtained from the stimulus[35]. ‘Reward value’ is, in classical conditioning, the ‘reinforcer’, the stimulus that rewards the conditioned behaviour. ‘Positive incentive value’ simply refers to the governing of behaviour via expectations, which may mirror in some ways the effect of a positive ‘art-hood’ classification in the Pelowski study.

Hargreaves and North consider ‘arousal states goals’ as a specific aesthetic function of music[12]. Where a specific arousal level is sought after that is context dependent, they found that subjects usually choose music to moderate their arousal level, but stress that, although it is an integral component, arousal simply does not present a complete psychological model. They draw heavily from and often point towards the work of Martindale [36], who in their eyes presents a context inclusive model.

Martindale’s theory is centred around the idea that one’s likes and dislikes are based on preference for prototypes; this itself was based on the early idea of neural networks. For Martindale et al. the mind is comprised of interconnected cognitive units, or modules, each of which stores the representation of a different object. Modules coding more prototypical stimuli are activated more frequently because these stim-

uli are experienced most frequently than those coding atypical stimuli. This leads them to the proposal that aesthetic preference is “a positive function of the degree to which the mental representation of a stimulus is activated. Because more typical stimuli are coded by mental representations capable of greater activation, preference should be positively related to prototypicality”. The significance of their work is the argument that the prototypicality of an art object is a stronger determinant of preference than the arousal-evoking qualities. This model will provide a psychological imperative for the compression progress models that will be discussed in Section 2.5.

2.4 Neuroaesthetics

Neuroaesthetics as understood by Pearce et al[37], who wrote a literature review of the field, is the cognitive neuroscience of aesthetic experience. Their approach advocates the study of “a wide spectrum of aesthetic experiences, resulting from interactions of individuals, sensory stimuli, and context”. They also attempt to reconcile the study with approaches and criticism that come from the humanities; in contemporary discourse, the two appear as almost completely divergent fields of study. They cite Killeen’s interpretation of Aristotle’s ‘four causes’ of behaviour. Killeen argues that complex forms of cognition and behaviour call for efficient, material, formal, and final explanations[38]. Efficient causes refer to the external trigger; material causes to the anatomy and physiology underlying the behaviour; Formal causes to the formal models of behaviour (see Leder above [33]); and final causes refer to the function of the behaviour (in an evolutionary sense). The reconciliation here is that all four are necessary to explain a behaviour and that neuroscience largely only focuses on the material causes.

The authors also make a crucial specification, that art and aesthetics overlap, both conceptually and historically, but that they are not identical, this distinction is drawn from the influential art-critic and philosopher Arthur Danto[39]. Following from this, they address the distinctions between two overlapping but different sub-fields; the cognitive neuroscience of aesthetics, and the cognitive neuroscience of art. The cognitive neuroscience of aesthetics is the study of the evolutionary foundations

of the aesthetic experience. The cognitive neuroscience of art, on the other hand, is the study of the neurocognitive and evolutionary mechanisms by which humans are able to engage with art at many different levels, in addition to the purely aesthetic level.

Pearce illuminates the issue of the variance the aesthetic experience through time. He cites both Beethoven's *Symphony No. 9* and Stravinsky's *Le Sacre du Printemps* as pieces whose first audience had vastly different experiences upon listening to the work than a contemporary one would. The issue at large here is that a cognitive neuroscience of aesthetics must be able to account for varieties of such experience across cultures and historical periods, otherwise, it is empirically redundant.

Shusterman offers a less historically contingent approach. He proposes that there are three crucial components of the aesthetic experience[40]. An evaluation dimension, it involves the evaluation of an object; a phenomenological dimension, in that one's attention, is drawn, it is subjectively felt; and a semantic dimension, the experience has meaning, as opposed to simply involving sensation.

The question that naturally follows a discussion of the psychology and cognitive neuroscience of the aesthetic experience, is whether there are brain areas that are specifically engaged in this activity? What are the anatomical correlates of the aesthetic experience? In other words, if we find the behaving differently when there are aesthetic judgments involved, then they do effectively "exist" as physical entities (within the brain) and can be empirically characterised.

Furthermore, although in the previous sections we reviewed some of the arguments for the pleasure of aesthetics being attributed to the neural circuitry for reward, what accounts for the subjectivity in aesthetic reward sensitivity still remains unclear. There has been substantial research involving brain imaging techniques such as functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) and diffusion tensor imaging (DTI) to illuminate and map brain this activity.

The research largely takes the form of some questionnaire evaluation to establish a ground truth, before the subjects are presented the same stimuli again but in-

side under brain imaging. Jacobson et al. conducted one of the initial studies; concerned with the effect of symmetry in geometric shapes. Their participants performed aesthetic judgments and descriptive symmetry judgments on the same stimuli before performing the same task under fMRI. Their behavioural results confirmed the influence of geometric symmetry and complexity on aesthetic judgments. Direct comparisons of stimuli showed specific activations for aesthetic judgments in the frontomedian cortex, bilateral prefrontal, and posterior cingulate, left temporal pole, and the temporoparietal junction. Judgments of beauty enhanced blood-oxygen-level-dependent (BOLD) signals in the frontomedian cortex, but also in the left intraparietal sulcus of the symmetry network. Significantly and perhaps surprisingly, these findings suggest that aesthetics judgements rely on a network that partially overlaps with that which is used in processing social and moral cues[41, 42].

Kawabata and Zeki sought to address whether the specific brain regions were active when subjects viewed the paintings that they had previously evaluated as beautiful, regardless of their style (portrait, still life, abstract expressionism etc). Their results prove their hypothesis, that the orbitofrontal cortex was found to be differentially engaged during the perception of stimuli evaluated as ‘beautiful’ compared to ‘ugly’, crucially this was regardless of the style of painting[43].

Preferences for paintings were found to have significantly different neuroanatomical correlates. Vartanian and Goel conducted fMRI imaging on subjects who had given a preferential evaluation of painting and digitally doctored painting[44]. They found that in response to decreasing preference, activation in right caudate nucleus decreased but that activation in bilateral occipital gyri, left cingulate sulcus, and bilateral fusiform gyri increased in response to increasing preference. They thus draw the conclusion that the aforementioned brain structures response to preference is evidence of their roles in evaluating reward-based stimuli.

Green et al. studied the results of the ‘mere exposure effect’ on the neuroanatomical correlates of music listeners[45]. The ‘mere exposure effect’ is the psychological phenomenon which explains the tendency to develop a preference merely through familiarity alone (for more on this see [46]). The subjects first participated in a

‘learning phase’, where systematic and varied exposure to melodies was conducted. Following this, subjects rated liking for each melody whilst inside a fMRI scanner. It was found that melodies heard most often were most the liked, providing evidence in favour of the ‘mere exposure effect’. In the bilateral dorsolateral prefrontal and inferior parietal cortex neural activations were found as a function of previous exposure, which was assumed to reflect retrieval and working memory-related processes.

Sachs et al. conducted further work, combining survey data, behavioural and psychophysiological measures and diffusion tensor imaging on listeners grouped into those that felt ‘chills’ when listening to series of musical pieces and those that did not[28]. ‘Chills’ were the self-reported psychophysical response to a profound aesthetic experience. From the imaging, they found that white matter connectivity between sensory processing areas in the superior temporal gyrus and emotional and in the insula and medial prefrontal cortex, structures associated with social processing was significantly more active in the ‘chills’ group than the control. Their findings provide evidence for a neural basis of individual differences in sensory access to the reward system.

Surveying the literature displays the dizzying variety of results from the research. What can be said conclusively, however, is that no single brain region is used for the encoding of aesthetic information or for producing the aesthetic experience and that aesthetic judgements are the result of different patterns of activation than the ones resulting from just simply hearing music or seeing pictures. Furthermore, the involvement of the frontal lobe in this processes is unanimously agreed upon.

2.5 Compression Progress

The most intellectual activities of modern humans are clear manifestations of extremely sophisticated information compression, it is the principal aim of science for example. Scientific insight aims to relate a phenomenon to some sort of predictive understanding of our environment, here, the environment could be as little as a sub-atomic quantum state or as large as the entire universe. The greatest scientific

insights are those that manage to wrap up, or, compress many apparently diverse environmental observations and sometimes even other scientific insights into compact laws.

Accounts of the most powerful and novel information compression mechanisms - scientific breakthroughs - nearly always suggest that there is a visceral thrill to it. Descriptions of the best applications of information compression lends themselves to emotive language (“*cracking the code*”, “*unlocking the secret*”, “*breaking through*”). This is a wholly intrinsic pleasure, which is not to be confused with an extrinsic pleasure, i.e. financial remuneration, or institutional or social reward.

Schmidhuber and later Hudson propose that information compression could be an all-encompassing theory of aesthetic pleasure. Schmidhuber argues that data itself becomes temporarily interesting to a self-improving but computationally limited, subjective observer. He argues that our native curiosity is moved by a desire to create or discover (to produce or interpret) non-random, non-arbitrary, regular data. That is, codified and organised data that is novel and surprising; this being the result of a compression process. This drive maximises ‘interestingness’[47, 2].

Schmidhuber posits that ‘all active creation and attentive perception of artwork are just by-products of our principle of interestingness and curiosity yielding reward for compressor improvements’. The artificial observer must perceive art ‘sequentially’ and actively. For humans, this means the regular shifting of our attention through features.

The difference for the agent in effectively adapting the compressor in the practice of doing science opposed to creating or observing art is that in science, it is essential that new shorter expression is third person verifiable, in art this is not the case. In art, the result of the compression may be subconscious, something we may not be able to communicate but feel.

Schmidhuber lists the ingredients of a formal framework of analysis of his theory. First, a continually improving predictor or compressor works on the continually growing data history, a computable measure of the compressor’s progress (to calcu-

late intrinsic rewards), and a reward optimizer or reinforcement learner translating rewards into action sequences expected to maximise future reward.

Building on the work of Schmidhuber, Hudson, outlines a method of measuring the ‘beauty’ in music. He posits that the compressibility of a digital recording of a piece of music, which he takes to be the discrete representation of its form, could be used as a measure of ‘beauty’[25].

Hudson argues that the relationship between the listener’s pleasure is directly comparable to the ratio of maximum lossless audio compression in the audio track. His hypothesis is that the measure of this deficit between the perceived complexity (and thus perceived incompressibility) of a work and the actual compressibility of a work that we find aesthetic pleasure. This is his material comparison to the Schmidhuber cognitive model.

However, Hudson doesn’t back the hypothesis up with a comprehensive study, thus we are left to simply examine the logic of the proposal. If we, for instance, consider what the psychological literature advances to be the most lauded theories of understanding how the brain organises and sorts sensory data we see clearly that underlying logic is strikingly different.

If we consider Gestalt principles, an example of one such approach, to parse the sensory by data seeking the most salient information; lossless data compression algorithms take a subtractive approach, they remove data that is considered statistically redundant.

Compression based estimates are further expanded by Svängård and Nordin [48] and by Bies et al[49]. These works on compression and complexity are explored formally through several different formulations that include fractal density, RMS value and Kolmogorov complexity.

Machado and Cardoso outline a holistic theory for measuring aesthetic value[1]. Like Schmidhuber and Hudson, their theory is based around the encoding of internal representations of art objects. Their theory is implemented on visual art but could

also be implemented in music. They define it as such: “the aesthetic value of an artwork is directly connected to Image Complexity (IC) and inversely connected to Processing Complexity (PC)”. This is very similar to Schmidhuber’s theory- ‘what seems to complex at first but turns out to quite parsable, is aesthetically pleasing’. In order to test our theory, they devise estimates for IC and PC, and having these estimates, developed a formula (a and b, can be used to change the importance given to each factor):

$$aesthetic\ value = \frac{IC^a}{(PC)^b}$$

Machado and Cardoso hold that the IC remains constant for a given image, but add in their second iteration that the PC should increase over time, where t_0 is time at the start of the experiment and t_1 is sometime later, they construct the following formula to take this into account:

$$aesthetic\ value = \frac{IC^a}{(PC(t_0) * PC(t_1))^b * \left(\frac{PC(t_1) - PC(t_0)}{PC(t_1)}\right)^c}$$

Like Hudson, they initially used a standard compression algorithm (jpg) to estimate the compression progress. However, they later believed fractal image compression to be closer to the way that humans encode image data than jpg compression. To test their implementation they used TDA (Test of Drawing Appreciation), a psychological test that assesses the aptitude to evaluate artistic structures. The test tries to estimate the level in which an individual recognises and reacts to the basic principles of aesthetic order: unity, dominance, variety, balance, continuity, rhythm, symmetry and proportion. The average scores in this test are 45.680 (for professionals of several activities) and 55.6897 (for Fine Arts graduates) and answering randomly would result in an average of 43.47. Machado and Cardoso’s program TDA score varied from 49 to 66 with an average score of 58.6.

Compression progress appears to be the most fruitful avenue in computational aesthetics at this moment, but it faces a single crucial obstacle. Until we understand

more about how our brain compresses and encodes information there's no way we can build a machine proxy. This is essential to building a better model.

2.6 Summary Statistics

McDermott et al.[50] conducted several experiments for a theory of information compression in auditory perception. Their results show that the compact storage of sensory signals' structure, or temporal detail is encoded using time-averaged statistics.

Though their results point towards a more general use of time averaging in auditory perception, the audio content tested here is what the author calls 'sound textures', which they define as: "the superposition of many similar acoustic events, collectively giving rise to aggregate statistical properties". The examples used for testing were generated using time-averaged statistically analysed recordings. The original recordings and the perceived source of the synthesised sounds could be described as urban or natural, steady and featureless, for example, the sound of a fire, a stream, a swarm of insects, a fan, a crowded bar, the steady state of an engine, etc.

The experiments assessed the ability of listeners to discriminate these texture examples. The author's hypothesis proposes that if the representation of sound textures are stored exclusively as time-averaged statistics then signals with distinct statistical properties (i.e. textures generated from the statistical analysis of a recording of fire and insects) should be discriminated well. However, signals with similar statistical properties (i.e. those generated from the same statistical data - fireA and fireB) should be indistinguishable.

The results indicate that once the sounds are of moderate length, the brains representation is limited to time-average statistics. This was evident given that when subjects were asked to discriminate examples of a different texture, their performance improved with excerpt duration, but conversely when subjects were asked to discriminate examples of the same texture, their performance declined with duration. For different examples of the same texture the, time-averaged statistics converge to

the same values with increasing duration.

McDermott et al. propose a dual model for auditory representation. One where detail stored explicitly, but whose memory capacity is limited, and one in which temporal detail is continuously compressed into summary statistics. In other words, the signal that enters the ears is continuously encoded, and once memory capacity is reached, its contents are overwritten. At that point, previous temporal detail is available only as summary statistics.

It could be possible that stimuli with higher compressibility leave more space for detailed information to be stored explicitly. This would mean that stimuli that induce the aesthetic experience also leaves a much more specific representation in the mind.

2.7 Global Sensory Properties

Brattico et al. define their term ‘global sensory’ qualities as those which concern the “whole sound - distinct from any of its individual parts, instruments, harmony, structure, intervals, melody, or tuning”. Furthermore, ‘global sensory’ qualities are largely not grounded in Western or non-Western music theory, for example, perceptual acoustic dimensionality, which covers not only the sound of spaces but colloquial descriptors such as “*tight*”, “*full*”, “*thin*” etc, and thus they should be devoid of any enculturation process. The traditional study of aesthetic value in music largely omits considerations of perceptual acoustic dimensionality due to a belief that the essence of a work is located wholly in the symbolic data that provides instruction for its realisation, the score. Largely that which a composer has communicated, or sometimes more generously that which an interpreter, a player, embellishes. The concept is not new when considered in the context of visual art, the theory that a “significant form” was present in the art objects that evoke an ‘aesthetic experience’ in the viewer has a longer history[42, 51].

Brattico et al. detail several types of ‘global sensory property’ and present a biological/evolutionary rationale for them. There are two main features they focus on:

‘the distribution of spectral energy’ and ‘musical texture’[52].

Their reasoning for focus on ‘the distribution of spectral energy’ is apparent in a psychoacoustic phenomenon known as auditory masking, where tones activating cells situated too close together on the basilar membrane have the effect of cancelling one and other out. Thus, with the aim of seeking auditory clarity, we have built a preference for well-distributed spectral energy. For a reference on masking look to Zwicker[53].

With ‘musical texture’ the rationale is less clear. They define musical texture as a whole Gestalt percept formed of the coalescence of ‘local’ musical features such as rhythm, melody, harmony and arrangement. It is strange here that they don’t include timbre since the instrumentation of a composition surely changes the musical texture? They also soften their position on the exclusion of symbolic information, i.e. that music theory is in itself enough to elicit an aesthetic experience citing the work of McDermott and Simoncelli[50].

They also list several other possibly contributory features but give none the emphasis of the former two. The aesthetic experience is affected by exposure and familiarity (see ‘mere exposure effect’ [45] in Section ??). Contributory though exposure may be to the aesthetic experience, it is not a quality of the object itself and thus is neither testable at the source or particularly relevant to a discussion of its properties.

Alluri[54] et al. is highlighted here also. In their experiment participants were asked to consciously listen to a piece of music whilst under fMRI scanning. The data from which was then correlated with statistical properties extracted from the piece. They list 6 final features that positively correlate with a ‘musical experience’ (Fullness, Brightness, Timbral complexity, Key clarity, Pulse clarity, Activity, and Dissonance). It remains to be seen, however, whether this approach can be directly applied to the study of aesthetics.

We see Bell’s[9] lasting impression in the work of Zeki[55] who interprets the theory of a ‘significant form’ through the distribution of neural processing of visual stimuli across several quasi-independent brain modules, each of specialised in a different

domain (movement, colours, lines, faces, direction, etc.). Each of these domains has a “biologically derived combination of elements for the attribute that it is specialized in processing”. Sachs hypothesis[28] is that a “preferential” pattern of activation across these brain modules is perceived as an aesthetic experience. The authors see no reason to believe that what is true for visual art would not be true of music.

A sonic object that evokes spatial and affective cognition (across the relevant brain modules), that features a distribution of energy over the whole frequency spectrum (aiding clarity), that holds the listener’s attention through a balance of familiarity and novel material will provide the listener with an immersive experience and continuous arousal. Further, this preference for clarity is critical to the successful encoding of the auditory data at higher levels of brain functioning. The preferences for successfully encodable audio stimulus is known as the ‘fluency processing hypothesis’ (for more see [56]). A problem alloying this theory with what we have already discussed is that a dull, unsaturated but fluently processed sonic is not as appealing as a complex one that incorporates the whole frequency and spatial spectrum. The authors suggest that this may possibly be reconciled with the ‘immersion hypothesis’ (see [44]), that there are really multiple preferences at play, ‘competing interests’ if you will. That fluency must be balanced with engagement[57].

2.8 Summary

This review hopes to have provided a very short introduction to the development of computational aesthetics, from its origins to the most compelling contemporary theory. We have shown how the ideas of Plato, Pythagoras etc. laid the foundations for a theory of beauty that relates to geometry, space, numerical relations and form. How a debate opened up by enlightenment thinkers regarding subjectivity and objectivity in the personal derivation of pleasure from beauty remains unresolved, but has largely become translated into a discussion on the relevance of the properties of the subject and of the object.

We’ve outlined how Kant presented a nascent form of the idea that the basic building

blocks of cognition used in harmonious ways produce the aesthetic experience, and how this was matched by Herbert's suggestion that the basic building blocks of composition hold no aesthetic value of their own but can be used in harmonious ways to create aesthetic value.

We've detailed how in the 20th-century aesthetics split into a, largely sociocultural study, and a new empirical study. But that even in the new empirical study, the inner dialect of the field- the mutually exclusive studies of subject and object- are yet to be synthesised.

We have presented several theories and adaptive reasonings for the existence of aesthetic experience. The most convincing and holistic point towards a reward system for the successful encoding of visual, literary or musical information, and that these developed amongst and made use of a broader arsenal of comprehension tools. This has meant that there doesn't necessarily have to be a direct function for aesthetic comprehension in sexual selection but rather it displays aptitude in a broader set of cognitive functions.

It was therefore argued that this was built through growth in both the sensory properties and comprehensive abilities and the aesthetic forms used for communication; a cyclical arms race, each growing with every cycle with no need for either to be a priori.

This has meant that measuring the encodability of an art object has become the paramount task in computational aesthetics, and information compression appears to have become the dominant proxy for implementations of this.

One of the crucial differences between the aesthetic tradition in the humanities and the scientific/empirical aesthetic tradition is we believe the causes much of the friction between them, furthermore, it seems to be almost unconsidered and unspoken. It is that they believe they are measuring the same thing, they are not. One considers and measures the aesthetic value of the work from the point of a philosophical abstraction; the work is for them, unbound from a material reality, often equated to an extension of the artist or composers will. The other does the

opposite, measuring it at the point of experience; the work is the stimuli whose neural encoding manifests itself in the aesthetic experience.

These are two different points in the journey the art object takes through its inception and materialisation. A lot of changes happen along this journey, and little has been done to take account of this. Before there can be any real success in measuring the value of whole compositions (in relation to one and other), we need to understand the effects on the aesthetic experience that come from decisions (or from by-products of decisions) that we may not consider to be ‘artistic’. These may occur in the later stages of the artistic intervention; in the performance, production, packaging, transmission or projection of the work. Without understanding the effects of these we will not be able to compare two different works independently of these factors.

2.9 Research Goals

These ‘non-artistic’ decisions and their effects on the aesthetic experience can be seen manifested in colloquial utterances that signal what Pelowski[32] calls the ‘hedonic reaction’: “*That cover band butchered one of my favourite band’s tracks!*” or, “*those speakers don’t do this track justice!*”. This can be taken as evidence that a single work can produce different aesthetic experiences. We can, therefore, propose that there exists a hierarchy of possible realisation of any one work. That is to say, that continuum exists between the artist ideal conception of their work and the worst. Along this continuum lies every conceivable expression of the work; every recording, every performance, on every medium of playback and through every HiFi.

2.9.1 The ‘work’ and the ‘object’

Now we have established the idea that there are multiple possible realisations of any given ‘work’ of art or composition. It would now be necessary to introduce some language we can use to discuss this; a delineation between the aesthetic value of the ‘work’ of art, and the aesthetic experience produced by an art ‘object’.

The ‘work’ (of art), is that which was previously referred to as the ‘ideal conception’, but could equally refer to the original material intervention of the artist (if such exists). This is clearest when considering the fine arts. A painting is a single material intervention; oil on canvas, the same is true of sculpture. The distinction gets a little more blurred if we consider photography for one photographic negative can produce multiple images; differing in an array of characteristics, to a multitude of degrees great and small. Which photograph is the original ‘work’?

Music, however, presents an even greater challenge to this objective. For who can say where the original ‘work’, the composition, lies? Is it the manuscript first published? Is it the premier concert? Is it the first produced recording? It is all of these and none at once. Perhaps if we were to allow ourselves to lean into a romanticised notion of composition, we could reach beyond the material and suggest it lies only inside the mind of the composer; in an immaterial ‘ideal conception’.

This is a critical problem for any work of computational or empirical aesthetics; from where does one sample that aesthetic measure? The traditional aestheticist, art or music critic tends to, unless they are reporting specifically on a concert or exhibition, consider the aesthetic value of the work from the point of a philosophical abstraction. The work is for them, unbound from a material reality. The neuroscientist does the opposite, measuring it at the point of experience.

Consider for a second, testing water quality: we may measure the pH level at any point along the river. Sampling at the point where it will be consumed will tell you if it’s safe to drink. But to truly understand what affects water quality we must understand the river’s ecology, geography, geology and its interactions with other sources.

The same is true of aesthetics. The source of the stream is the artist, but on its journey, it’s filtered through communication and information technology. These factors must be studied if we are going to gain a fuller understanding of the aesthetic experience.

To help conceptualise this we propose a novel framework for ascertaining aesthetic

value. An aesthetic value that features two combinatory components, one the forms the philosophical abstraction of the work - the 'content aesthetic' and another that is informed by the material reality of the 'object'- 'container aesthetic'. Their names are a crude neologism that reflects the idea that the content of 'the work' must be wrapped in some material form to ever reach an audience. The two occupy separate, but often overlapping, parts of the journey from the artist's initial conception, to the stimuli received and interpreted by the listener/viewer.

The former (the content) occupies the liminal space between and including the immaterial conception and the immediate and finalised material intervention. The aesthetic measure sampled here is the aesthetic value that the philosophy of aesthetic largely investigates. This is the aesthetic value of the work itself as if engaged with through a perfect unbiased, un-contaminative, perfect medium. However, the technology mediating the communication, be it be the orchestra or the iPod, is not passive in its transference. It acts on the aesthetic value of the work.

We can attribute this inconsistency to the aesthetics of 'the container'. This part of the aesthetic value constitutes everything between 'the work' in its abstract form and the receiver. In the fine arts, the later stage decisions are often out with the hands of the artist. The digital photograph of the sculpture that is viewed online, may or may not have been taken by the artist themselves, even if it was, the artist may have had no hand in tailoring the image compression used before its upload, nor the quality of display that the image is then viewed on. Each of these manipulations affected the aesthetic experience of the eventual viewer and are therefore aesthetic decisions.

There are of course clear parallel processes in music and audio, consider for example the journey the composition takes before reaching the ears of a modern music consumer: from recording, mixing, mastering through to file compression and streaming, digital to analogue conversion and projection (through speakers). This is by no means a complete or concrete list; for almost every instance of listening, a unique set of processes affect what eventually reaches the listener. What's more is the artist often has ever diminishing responsibility for the decisions made as this advances. And

to reiterate, these are aesthetic decisions since they affect the aesthetic experience of the listener.

2.9.2 Summary

A composition is realised in a unique environment almost every time it is listened to; a new performance, a streamed version instead of vinyl playback, a different hifi, a different room, a change in air temperature. Some of these are sweeping alterations, some of these are minute, but they all affect the aesthetic experience of the listener. This is the difference between the ‘work’ and the ‘object’. There cannot be progress in more accurately assessing the value of ‘the work’ without already understanding the factors that affect ‘the object’.

It is our hypothesis that this is the most likely place to find objectivity in the aesthetic experience (if it is to be found at all), for we are here examining the effects of the smallest of aesthetic decisions. Furthermore, it is hoped that what we can learn here about the smallest aesthetic decisions will inform the larger ones.

To do this we plan to study listeners ‘hedonic reaction’[32] to various transformed compositions via a questionnaire. The listeners will be presented and asked to rank, several version of the same compositions that have been transformed in a series of ways that represent various ‘degradations’ in the performance, production, transmission or projection of music. At the same time, statistical descriptors will be extracted from these, and the relationships between these descriptors and questionnaire results will be explored.

Chapter 3

Methods

This chapter will outline the methodology undertaken in our research. We plan to study listeners ‘hedonic reaction’[32] to various transformed compositions via a questionnaire. The listeners will be presented and asked to rank, several version of the same compositions that have been transformed in a series of ways that represent various ‘degradations’ in the performance, production, transmission or projection of music. At the same time, statistical descriptors will be extracted from these. We will describe our data collection procedure, the use of questionnaires and MIR tools, our investigation of the relationships between the results of each and finally our modelling procedures.

3.1 Listening Test

To collect responses of listeners a listening test was created using a Google questionnaire form. The premise of the listening test was very simple. Subjects were asked to rank five audio excerpts in regard to the “pleasurable sensation they gave rise to”. 1st rank being that version which was found to give rise to the most pleasurable experience and 5th that gave rise to the least pleasurable experience. This question was repeated five times per test, each time with five new versions of a new musical.

Each question featured five, manually transformed versions of the same composition. Each transformation is meant to uniquely ‘degrade’ the original in some way. A full description of the transformations is given in Section 3.1.1. The test was repeated once after the first collection of data, in order to collect more data in general and to invite subjects who had participated in the first iteration to repeat the test, to study them as a separate case.

We were seeking the broadest coalition of participants for the listening tests. After the five ranking questions, the participants were asked a series of demographic questions regarding their: age, degree of musical training, genre preference and listening habits.

Asking subjects to rank the versions explicitly, rather than say, asking them to evaluate their experience per track on a continuous or discrete sliding scale, allowed us to force them to make a value judgement. We wanted to avoid, for instance, a scenario where one stimulus was rated positively, one negatively and the rest largely undetermined. We conducted some initial test for our colleagues to try and gauge just how many versions could be presented and successfully ranked without a great deal of difficulty. We found that five could confidently be ordered without too much a fatigue.

For each question, a link was given to where a playlist was hosted, namely on the music streaming platform Soundcloud. This was preferred to linking to individual audio files hosted either on a Google Drive or elsewhere as we found that opening the files individual tabs on a web browser confused those we had asked to test our initial design.

UPF Research on Computational Aesthetics - Exploring objectivity in aesthetic judgements of 'audio quality'.

This questionnaire has five questions, for each question you're going to hear five slightly edited excerpts of the same piece of music. You are asked to simply rank the versions in order of the pleasurable sensation they give rise to (i.e. the most pleasurable being ranked 1st, and the least being ranked 5th). It should take no longer than 15 minutes.

Please take your time in coming to these judgements, you may listen to the excerpts as many times as you feel necessary.

We would ask that you listen to the excerpts in the most preferable listening conditions you have at your disposal (i.e. headphones and in a quiet environment; free from distracting stimulation, audio or visual).

Please set your volume to a comfortable level for the first excerpt and refrain from altering it throughout the experiment.

Once you've completed your ranking you'll be asked some follow up questions.

Your personal data (including email address) will not be shared with any third party.

Figure 1: Questionnaire preamble

Question 1

The following link will open a playlist in a new tab.

Access here:
<https://soundcloud.com/martindisley/sets/question-1>

Ranking *

	1st	2nd	3rd	4th	5th
Version A	<input type="radio"/>				
Version B	<input type="radio"/>				
Version C	<input type="radio"/>				
Version D	<input type="radio"/>				
Version E	<input type="radio"/>				

How difficult did you find this task?

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Easy. I had clear preferences.	<input type="radio"/>	Impossible. I had no preferences so just guessed.									

Figure 2: Questionnaire format

We were, however, aware of the potential bias that using this service may bring to our results; the Soundcloud platform may be more familiar to some participants than to others, and the kind of music that some participants listen to on that platform may inform their judgements during our test. However, due to the nature of the question, the ranking approach, any bias affects the rankings of each version equally. If we had asked subject to rank on a sliding scale we might see the bias appear as a generally lowered scoring for all versions. The term ‘aesthetics’ was deliberately omitted from the wording of this question so as to minimise the spread of assumptions and bias listeners may have brought in regard to what they believe the term ‘aesthetics’ to mean and imply. The participants were asked to maintain their volume at a comfortable and crucially, consistent level, throughout the duration of the test. The stimuli were never named; the tracks were titled simply by the corresponding radio button on the ranking interface (Version A, Version B etc.) and no information was given regarding the composer or artist, style or genre.

3.1.1 Transformations

As has been already stated, the audio files, subjects were asked to rank, were transformed versions of a single composition or recording. The original tracks were taken from Mike Senior’s ‘The Mixing Secrets’[58] download library¹, a mixing mastering tutorial that offers free multi-track recording resources. This was an appropriate test set because of both the breadth of genres available and the fact that the works were largely unknown, thus avoiding ‘the mere exposure effect’[46], which posits that prior exposure to an art object can increase the likelihood of having an aesthetic experience.

The transformations were chosen as proxies for the Alluri’s feature set[54] and Brattico’s Global Sensory Properties[52]. Not only this but they were also chosen to represent a variety of ‘real-life’ degradations, such as those that may occur as the composition makes its way from a philosophical abstraction to the material reality that meets the listener. The list of such degradations is near infinite but could in-

¹‘The ‘Mixing Secrets’ Free Multitrack Download Library’ access at: <http://www.cambridge-mt.com/ms-mtk.htm>

clude obvious filters such as the band-pass filtering of a telephone, the scrambling of content through faulty file decompression, or even poor room acoustics that blur or ‘muddy’ the sound. The rankings retrieved from the listening test could, again, give us an indication of what is absolutely essential for the aesthetic value of the content to be effectively communicated.

The tracks chosen account for a mix of genres, but all use western tonal structure, or extensions of it (to account for the inclusion of two jazz tracks). The harmonic structure of all should be familiar to the contemporary western (or international music) listener. The timbral and instrumental diversity is also quite within the confines of the traditional orchestra/choir or contemporary band setup. Two of the tracks feature some light electronic textures, which again we presume to sound familiar to the vast majority of our subjects. All of the selected works were instrumental, or at least instrumental sections were used

The tracks are listed below, the style that follows in parentheses is as it is listed on the collection:

1. Test 1

- (a) Bravestar: ‘Downtempo’ (Atmospheric Electronica)
- (b) Andrey Yaroshinky & The Gnessin Academy Chamber Orchestra: W.A. Mozart’s Piano Concerto No.12 K414 (Allegro) (Live Orchestral Recording)
- (c) James May: ‘All Souls Moon’ (Acoustic Singer-Songwriter)
- (d) Rod Alexander: ‘Tears In The Rain’ (Guitar Instrumental)
- (e) Zwiepack: ‘Air’ (Jazz Duo/Trio)

2. Test 2

- (a) Araujo: ‘The Saga Of Harrison Crabfeathers’ (Jazz)
- (b) Don Camillo Choir: ‘The Marsh Marigold’s Song’ (German Unaccompanied Choir)

- (c) Lorenzo Price: 'Changing Things (Dorian's Song)' (Jazz Fusion)
- (d) The Mountaineering Club Orchestra: 'Cruising The Ice' (Ambient Indie Instrumental)
- (e) Tall Heights: 'Spirit Cold' (Electrofolk)

Tracks from the data set come in the form of multitrack zip files, so before the transformed version could be created, a mixed and cut reference version had to be. This reference version was not going to be explicitly ranked within the listening test but provided the material the transformed versions were generated from. The length of these reference versions, which would set the length of the transformed version, was between 40 seconds to a minute. This was a difficult trade-off, for, on the one hand, differing length stimulus could bias the experiment, on the other, however, abruptly ending some samples in the middle of a phrase, would also bias the experiment.

It is crucial to note that the reference track was assumed to be ranked higher above any of the transformed version as the types of transformation were aimed at degrading the audio in some way. Evidence for this assumption came from the initial experiments with colleagues, who were presented with the reference version alongside the transformed versions. The initial tests proved that the reference track always came out on top. Furthermore, excluding the reference track from the those to be ranked allowed us in effect to have a ranking of 6 version per question, with the reference track's ranking being implicit.

The choice of transformation was influenced by the following considerations:

1. That they have the least overlap in statistical fluctuation
2. That they relate in some way to both Alluri's feature set[54] and Brattico's Global Sensory Properties[52]
3. They add as little stylistic input as possible

We will now describe the types of transformations and the processing techniques employed. The listening test was repeated twice, each time the same type of trans-

formation for each version was sought after, but the processing technique was slightly altered for the second test (In the following list ‘a’ refers to test 1 and ‘b’ to test 2). This was done in order to attempt to diminish the overfitting of the data towards the plugin, or processing technique used, but rather than the transformation type at large.

1. **Version A: Band-pass filtering.** Brattico[52] cite the ‘spread of spectral energy’ as a key component in the induction of the aesthetic experience through audio. This is replicated by band limiting the frequency content.
 - (a) The native Logic Pro EQ plugin was used: *lowpass* = 200Hz, *Q Value* = 24dB/Oct, *lowpass* = 2000Hz, *Q Value* = 24dB/Oct
 - (b) The Waves SSLEQ plugin was used: *lowpass* = 200Hz, *Q Value* = 2.5, *lowpass* = 2000Hz, *Q Value* = 2.5

Figure 3: Native Logic Pro EQ plugin

2. **Version B: Distortion.** By distorting the audio we increase the complexity of the audio signal and at the same time diminish the ease of it’s neural encoding. Distortion, here, implies the addition or exaggeration of harmonics. The compressibility of the stimuli, for Schmidhuber[2] is key to the aesthetic experience induced.

- (a) The native Logic Pro Bitcrusher plugin was used: *Drive* = 3.0dB, *Clip Level* = 0.0dB, *Resolution* = 8bit, *Downsampling* = 1x
- (b) The native Logic Pro Phase Distortion was used: *Mix* = 71%, *Intensity* = 19%, *Cutoff* = 1300Hz, *Resonance* = 65%

Figure 4: Native Logic Pro ‘BitCrusher’ plugin

3. **Version C: Harmonic Randomisation.** Alluri et al[54] cite both tonal clarity and dissonance as features that correlate highly with the induction of the aesthetic experience.

- (a) The Mammut Software’s Block Swapping² function was used: *Number of Swaps* = 54, *Block Size* = 1.23%
- (b) Mammut’s Block Swapping function was used again: *Number of Swaps* = 30, *Block Size* = 2.1%

Figure 5: Mammut software ‘Block Swapping’ interface

4. **Version D: Audio Compression.** A severe application of dynamic compression nearly ‘squares off’ the waveform, leaving the signal almost without dynamic complexity.

²Randomly selected regions of the spectrum and interchanges their values with that of their half(Hz). The Block size parameter sets the size of the blocks, given as a percentage of the whole frequency axis. The software can be accessed from here: <http://www.notam02.no/web/prosjekter/mammut/?lang=en>

- (a) The native Logic Pro Compression plugin was used several times on the same ‘maxed out’ settings: *Compressor Threshold* = -40dB, *Ratio* = 24:1, *Attack* = 5.0ms, *Release* = 51.0ms, *Circuit Type* = ‘Vintage VCA’
- (b) The Waves ‘C1 Comp’ was used in the same routing as above: *Ratio* = 32:1, *Attack* = 2.0ms, *Release* = 50.0ms

Figure 6: Waves C1 Compressor plugin

5. **Version E: Transient Reduction.** Alluri et al[54] list both rhythmic clarity and event synchronicity as features crucial to inducing the aesthetic experience through audio. By reducing the audibility of the transients we aim to degrade both these features.

- (a) Eventide’s Physion plugin was used and routed back through itself four times: *Focus* = 100% Transient, *Smoothing* = 50%
- (b) Michael Norris’ Spectral Granulation plugin was used: *Grain Length* = 0.165s, *Grain Delay* = 0.37s, *Grain Delay Variance* = 0.05s, *Density* = 66%,

Figure 7: Michael Norris' Spectral Granulation plugin

3.2 Feature Retrieval

Following the generation of the transformed versions, the statistical features for each track were computed using Essentia's Music Extractor. Essentia is an open-source C++ library with Python bindings for audio analysis and audio-based music information retrieval. The library contains a large collection of algorithms which implement standard digital signal processing blocks, statistical characterisation of data and a large set of spectral, temporal, tonal and high-level music descriptors[59]. We used Music Extractor function which computes a large set of spectral, time-domain, rhythm, tonal and high-level descriptors automatically. Those features that are highly correlated with the induction of the aesthetic experience through audio is the matter under question, so it was important to take as many features into consideration.

Music Extractor's output gave 125 aggregated, mean and standard deviation values

for each audio file³, that is for each version and the reference track for every question.

3.3 Pearson Correlation

In order to examine the relationship between the Essentia feature statistics and the rankings retrieved from the listening test, we computed the Pearson correlation coefficient for each feature against the ranking. The Pearson correlation coefficient is a measure of the linear correlation between two variables X and Y. Returned values lie between -1 and +1, where +1 is a total positive linear correlation, 0 is no linear correlation, and -1 is a total negative linear correlation. When applied to a population is commonly represented by ρ and where σ_X is the standard deviation of X and σ_Y is the standard deviation of Y:

$$\rho_{X,Y} = \frac{\text{cov}(X,Y)}{\sigma_Y \sigma_X}$$

It would be reasonable to expect here that those features that are affected by more than one kind of transformation to have the strongest relationship to the rankings, as opposed to those that are more closely associated with a single transformation. For example, we would expect the ‘tonal’ features⁴ values to change most when calculated for all ‘Version C’s as the transformation (harmonic randomisation) will affect the harmonic structure. However, this will likely not prove to have a strong relationship with the rest of the rankings as their harmonic structure remains largely unaltered. We predict that ‘low-level’ features that are affected by the largest numbers of transformations will be the most strongly correlated.

3.4 Predictive Modelling

After gathering the necessary data from two sources- the rankings from the listening test responses and the statistical features from the Essentia Music Extractor output-

³The full list of computed features and the documentation for the algorithm can be accessed here: http://essentia.upf.edu/documentation/streaming_extractor_music.html

⁴Tonal features: http://essentia.upf.edu/documentation/streaming_extractor_music.html#tonal

the next step is to explore predictive modelling techniques. The task of predicting the how a new version of a composition, used in the data collection, or out-with, would be ranked is a supervised machine learning (ML) task, as both the example inputs and outputs are presented.

The example outputs are presented as distinct classes (1st, 2nd ... 5th), but as has already been stated, this was merely a method of forcing subjects to make an explicit judgement. This means the task of modelling can be thought of as both a classification and regression task. If we imagine the ranks as only fixed classes (1st, 2nd ... 5th), we could try and group testing items with neighbours in these classes. On the other hand, if we view the ranking as a continuous scale, one could imagine if a sixth item was introduced it may be ranked somewhere between one of 5 items already ranked. To treat the problem as such would be to treat it as a regression task.

Both of these approaches were implemented, the following chapters will discuss the results of each and the merits that each approach brings to the problem.

3.4.1 WEKA

To perform the modelling we employed WEKA or the “Waikato Environment for Knowledge Analysis”[60]. Weka is a collection of ML tools for data mining tasks developed by the Wakaito University from New Zealand. Weka contains tools for data pre-processing, classification, regression, clustering, association rules, and visualisation.

3.4.2 Simple Linear Regression

A simple linear regression is a statistical process for estimating the relationships among variables. The simple linear regression model seeks to find the best fitting line, *the regression line*, through an n-dimensional space, where n is the number of predictor variables[61]. The linear regression is one of the oldest and simplest predictive modelling techniques its major drawback is in its assumption that the

relationships in question are linear.

The linear regression will output a series of weighted correlation coefficients, one for each feature, and also a general correlation coefficient. The weighting of the individual features will give us another account of the relationships between those features and the ranking. The general correlation coefficient will, however, be used as our metric for evaluating the results.

3.4.3 Support Vector Machine

A Support Vector Machine (SVM) model is another ML approach more commonly used for a classification test. SVM works by building a representation of the examples as points mapped so that the examples of the separate classes are divided by a gap that is as wide as possible. New examples are then mapped into that same space and predicted to belong to a category based on which side of the gap they fall[62]. We will use the SVM for classification and a modified version, an SMO Regressor for the regression task. Again, the function outputs a general correlation coefficient which will be used as our metric of evaluation.

3.5 Normalised Compression Distance

Another approach was considered; an elementary investigation into the theories of Machado and Cardoso [1, 63], who draw upon the work of Hudson[25] and Schmidhuber[2]. All of the above correlate, in a variety of ways, the aesthetic experience and information compression. In general, they make the argument that the aesthetic experience is triggered by the successful encoding of stimuli in the mind. Schmidhuber explicitly calls this process ‘compression progress’. The degree of the aesthetic experience it, therefore, the degree to which a work, which upon first exposure seems especially complex, can indeed be encoded successfully. This relates to the notion of Kolmogorov complexity; the shortest expression of information that produces the desired output.

Normalized compression distance (NCD) is a way of measuring the similarity be-

tween two objects. Here though the definition of similarity between two objects is the difficulty of transforming them into each other. This is interesting in regard to this research as it provides us with an information theory related estimation of the effect of our transformations.

The formula for such a computation is as such, where x and y are binary string inputs and Z is the compressor:

$$NCD_Z(x, y) = \frac{Z(xy) - \min\{Z(x), Z(y)\}}{\max\{Z(x), Z(y)\}}$$

The implementation used here utilised a modified Python powered NCD calculator written by Aleph Melo⁵. Melo's 'pyncd' implementation uses the LZMA python class⁶ which provides functions for compression and decompression of data using the LZMA compression algorithm, which is very similar to the Bzip2 algorithm.

NCD has been used by Helen et al[64], amongst others, as an audio similarity metric. Foster et al[65] have even proposed its use as a method of cover song identification. However, it relates most clearly in our case to Hudson's theory of musical beauty[25], where he argues that a ratio of complexity to compressibility could form the basis of an aesthetic measure.

Here we will compute the NCD between each version and its reference track to compare their similarity, in terms of information theory, with their ranking.

⁵Aleph Melo's original python code can be accessed here: <https://github.com/alephmelo/pyncd>

⁶<https://docs.python.org/3/library/lzma.html>

Chapter 4

Results

This chapter will discuss the results of the listening test followed by some statistical analysis of both the rankings and the relationships between the rankings and the statistical data. Finally, we will present the results of our predictive modelling.

4.1 Listening Test Responses

In this section, the discussion will focus on the listening test response data.

4.1.1 Response and demographics

The first iteration of the listening test received 28 responses, the second received 24 responses, which gave us 52 responses total. Approximately 30% of those that took the first test also participated in the second iteration. The break down of the demographic questions is as follows:

Participants varied in age (see Figure 8); the youngest grouping (18-24 years old) makes up the largest block, with every older grouping's contributing a smaller and smaller percentage of the sample size. Following each ranking question, subjects were asked how difficult they found the task of ranking. It is interesting, and positive for the significance of the older subjects rankings, that there was no significant correlation between the age of the participant ($r = -0.19$, $p = < .005$).

Figure 8: What is your age?

Figure 9: How many hours per week do you spend ‘attentively’ listening to music?

The following questions explored the listening and music making habits of the participants. The second question asked “[h]ow many hours per week do you spend ‘attentively’ listening to music?”, the results of which can be seen in Figure 9. We believe that the answers here should be taken with ‘a pinch of salt’. That is to say, we don’t believe they were wholly truthful. Exactly a third of the participants claimed to listen ‘attentively’ to music for more than 10 hours per week, we believe this is too many. It would certainly appear that for their extra hours of experience they don’t seem to find the task too much easier; there was no significant correlation between the number of hours listened by the participant and the difficulty of the ranking task ($r = 0.20$, $p = < .005$).

The next question asked the listeners about the technological mediums they often use to listen to music. This was insightful as we are, through the process of ranking transformed or degraded versions, considering degraded forms of communicating aesthetic value.

In a previous chapter, a delineation was proposed between two forms of aesthetic

value: the ‘content aesthetic’ and the ‘container aesthetic’. Where the ‘content aesthetic’ is the aesthetic value of the work as a philosophical abstraction, and the ‘container aesthetic’ is the effect of the materialised form on the work as an abstract form. The medium of playback would be once such affecting filter through which the abstract becomes concrete. It was, therefore, important to gather information about those mediums (filters) that participants have a degree of exposure to.

What we can see from the results, shown in Figure 10 is that the vast majority of participants listen to music, if not exclusively, in part through a digital device. Many of them also use what could be arguably considered slightly antiquated mediums such as vinyl and cassette. There was only a single participant whose answers suggested that they do not regularly listen to music on any digital device. Though this seemed not to have a great deal of effect on their rankings as they appeared to deviate from the average no more than any other. The vast majority of participants answered that they used a combination of mediums, with the majority of that group normally listening on digital devices sometimes with headphone or hi-fi speaker, and sometimes without, using the built-in speaker system. We would use these results to argue that the participants of our study are no more biased to one medium than another.

Figure 10: Through what medium(s) do you usually listen to music?

The final question participants answered was regarding their music making experience. A quarter of our subjects had ‘no such experience’. The rest had some degree of experience with music making. Another quarter previously had experience with music making but no longer play. 11% of our subject were formally trained musicians. The remaining 37% were non-professional players. It is therefore important to note therefore that our sample set was, in the majority, composed of music mak-

ers. However, this seemed to have little effect on their ranking, and their music making the experience (having some or none) was not significantly correlated with how difficult participants found the task ($r = -0.036$, $p = < .005$).

Figure 11: What experience do you have of music making?

4.1.2 Cleaning the data

After examining the results of the demographic questions, we examined the raw data from the rankings. From the two iterations of the test, we had a total of 10 questions, each with five versions ranked (50 columns of ranking data). The first test received 28 responses, the second received 24 responses, this means that not all versions have equal amounts of ranking data.

The first task of analysis was to examine the responses for each version. The average ranking was to be taken forward for the modelling, therefore, it was important to check that these averages legitimately represented the group. A histogram was generated for each version, two examples can be seen in Figure 12. What is clear from this analysis was that a clear trend was not always present. The two examples in Figure 12 show the extremes of this variance, (a) shows a clear trend- the bulk of the results are concentrated in one ranking, and there is generally skewing in that direction by those not. This is in clear contrast to Figure 12 (b), where the flat top suggests a near even spread of judgements, thus the subject group were as a whole unsure as to how this should be ranked. To clean the data and remove those unusable groups like that of Figure 12 (b) a logical operator was used.

(a) A clear trend

(b) No trend

Figure 12: two histograms of version ranking results

If the group's calculated variance value was greater than 1.1 and the percentage of units that equalled the value of mode of the group accounted for less than 40% of the group then it was deemed unusable. The reason a variance operator alone was not sufficient was to account for the possibility of a group with two peaks and a variance value of less than 1.1.

The result of this cleaning was that 13 of 50 versions and their rankings were removed. It was found that 12 of those fell below the threshold already mentioned, a further one was removed as it belonged to a question where all the other versions were removed. It made no sense to leave a single ranked version in the data set where all others, to act as references, to had been removed. Following this, the mode for each group whose rankings distribution proved to have a clear trend. The removal of the 13 groups hadn't greatly affected the distribution of average rankings for the versions. That is to say, that were not significantly fewer groups ranked 5th

than there were 2nd, for instance.

4.2 Statistical Analysis

A one way ANOVA test was run of every question; testing if the version type was significantly effecting the groups of rankings. The results are as follows:

1. Listening Test 1

(a) Q1: $F(4,130) = 31.63, p = 2.13E-18$

(b) Q2: $F(4,130) = 13.81, p = 2.05E-09$

(c) Q3: $F(4,130) = 29.55, p = 1.76E-17$

(d) Q4: $F(4,130) = 32.66, p = 7.75E-19$

(e) Q5: $F(4,130) = 30.14, p = 9.62E-18$

2. Listening Test 2

(a) Q1: $F(4,120) = 4.747961453, p = .001$

(b) Q2: $F(4,120) = 11.10039456, p = 1.07E-07$

(c) Q3: $F(4,120) = 33.38742394, p = 1.04E-18$

(d) Q4: $F(4,120) = 32.3337766, p = 2.82E-18$

(e) Q5: $F(4,120) = 15.75402635, p = 2.17E-10$

From the above list we can see that the version type was statistically significant in affecting the groups of rankings in every question ($p < \alpha, \alpha = .005$). Having already cleaned the data to remove the versions that had no trend in ranking, the average ranking was then considered for statistical significance. In Figure 13 you can see the mode rank for each question.

We also ran an ANOVA test on the modes, for when it came to training the model, it would be the modes that will be used. The results can be seen in Figure 14. We can, therefore, conclude that the averages are statistically significant since there's a

	Version A Mode	Version B Mode	Version C Mode	Version D Mode	Version E Mode
T1Q1	1	2	4	2	5
T1Q2	1	5	5	3	3
T1Q3	1	4	5	2	5
T1Q4	1	4	5	2	5
T1Q5	1	5	5	1	4
T2Q1	2	3	4	1	5
T2Q2	3	5	4	1	4
T2Q3	2	3	4	1	5
T2Q4	2	3	5	1	5
T2Q5	2	3	5	1	4
Mean	1.6	3.7	4.6	1.5	4.5
Mode	1	3	5	1	5
Std Dev	0.663324958	1.004987562	0.489897949	0.670820393	0.670820393
Variance	0.44	1.01	0.24	0.45	0.45
(Grand) Average	2	3	5	1	4

Figure 13: Average Ranking for the Version per Question

greater than chance likelihood that the version type is directly affecting the version averages ($F(25.9,93.48) = 40.6$, $p = 2.17E-14$)

Anova: Single Factor

Mode

SUMMARY

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
Version A Mo	10	16	1.6	0.48888889
Version B Mo	10	37	3.7	1.12222222
Version C Mo	10	46	4.6	0.26666667
Version D Mo	10	15	1.5	0.5
Version E Mo	10	45	4.5	0.5

ANOVA

Source of Variati	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Gro	93.48	4	23.37	40.6042471	2.17886E-14	2.57873918
Within Group	25.9	45	0.57555556			
Total	119.38	49				

Figure 14: ANOVA Results for the version modes

4.2.1 Ranking Results

Since the averages for each version proved to be significant we then looked at the ‘grand average’. This would be the overall average ranking of the transformed versions. This was not clear to calculate. In Figure 13 we can see the mean and mode for each of the versions. Neither gives us a clear average rank, where rank is the integer values from 1 to 5. The mode doesn’t really help either since it features

two 1's and two 5's. This leads us to use a ranking of the means instead. The results of this can be seen in the row '(Grand) Average'.

This average is certainly not as robust as the averaging of the versions alone, but it finally allows us to rank on average the versions themselves, an explanation of how these versions were created can be found in the methodology chapter 3.1.1. The following lists runs from most highly ranked to least:

1. [Version D] Audio Compression
2. [Version A] Band-pass filtering
3. [Version B] Distortion
4. [Version E] Transient Removal
5. [Version C] Harmonic Randomisation

4.2.2 Data Grouping

We now have multiple ways to combine the ranking data with the statistical data retrieved from the audio using Essentia. The following data sets were created by adding the ranking data as another column to the Essentia data:

1. Test1_VersionAverage: The Test 1 audio data with the average rankings from each version, in other words, the order of the ranking changes question to question.
2. Test1_GrandAverage: The Test 1 audio data with the grand averages as listed above, in other words, the order of the ranking is consistent throughout.
3. Test2_VersionAverage: The Test 2 audio data with the average rankings from each version.
4. Test2_GrandAverage: The Test 2 audio data with the grand averages as listed above.

5. Comb_VersionAverage: The Test 1 and Test 2 audio data with the average rankings from each version.
6. Comb_GrandAverage: The Test 1 and Test 2 audio data with grand averages as listed above.
7. Comb_SimplifiedAverage: The Test 1 and Test 2 audio data, this time where the ‘trend over the question’ ranking has been simplified so that 1st and 2nd become 1st, 3rd becomes 2nd and 4th and 5th become 3rd

4.3 Pearson Correlation

Following the creation of the datasets, we sought to investigate the relationship between the rankings (of every kind) and the Essentia statistics. To do this we calculated the Pearson correlation for each data set and for every Essentia feature. The top 10 features are listed in Figure 15, where the ranking is based on the mean value across each data set. The top 10 features a mixture of tonal, low-level loudness and spectral descriptors.

The spectral descriptor ‘lowlevel.spectral_contrast_valleys.stdev.mean’. peaks in Test1_GrandAverage, the distribution can be seen in Figure 16 ($r = 0.627$, $p = < .005$). It is always positively correlated, meaning that it increases as the ranking (number) does. That is to say that versions with a high ‘spectral contrast valleys standard deviation mean’ are much more likely to be ranked worse than those that do not. This descriptor captures the average standard deviation of the magnitude of valleys in the frequency spectrum. This means that the spectrum frequently changes, it could suggest modulation or noise, those preferred items would deviate away from noise or large and consistent changes in amplitude.

	Feature Name	Peak	Variance	Std Dev	Mean
1	tonal.hpcp_entropy.mean	0.590001201	0.004866098	0.069757421	0.448432823
2	lowlevel.loudness_ebu128.short_term.mean	-0.539671668	0.005784757	0.076057593	-0.448418923
3	tonal.hpcp_crest.mean	-0.586580209	0.003631798	0.0602644	-0.44760351
4	lowlevel.spectral_contrast_valleys.stdev.mean	0.62725575	0.01420318	0.119177095	0.433965583
5	lowlevel.loudness_ebu128.momentary.mean	-0.523980547	0.009724385	0.098612299	-0.408063576
6	tonal.hpcp.mean.mean	0.698511516	0.036330909	0.190606688	0.374443655
7	lowlevel.spectral_rms.stdev	0.482157644	0.004394627	0.066291984	0.372150076
8	tonal.hpcp.stdev.mean	0.487675389	0.008759027	0.093589671	0.356010621
9	tonal.hpcp.stdev.stdev	-0.537794919	0.013495335	0.116169425	-0.351232886
10	lowlevel.loudness_ebu128.short_term.stdev	0.562741854	0.026981351	0.16426001	0.313625071

Figure 15: Most highly correlated features (ranking based on mean value)

The descriptor that has the highest average correlation coefficient ($r = 0.45$, $p < .001$) is ‘tonal.hpcp_entropy.mean’; positively correlated, this means that higher the ranking of the item, the lower the value of this descriptor. HPCP or harmonic pitch class profiles are features based on a ‘pitch class profile’, which is a descriptor proposed in the context of a chord recognition system.

Another salient feature appears to be ‘lowlevel.loudness_ebu128.momentary.mean’. Again, much like the formerly mentioned feature, it ranks among the top five in all but Test2_VersionAverage. Conversely, however, it’s correlation is negative. Meaning that a version with a high value of loudness_ebu128.momentary.mean’ is strongly correlated with a high ranking. It’s peak correlation coefficient is in the Test1_GrandAverage dataset ($r = -0.51$, $p < .001$). A high value of this descriptor could likely mean that the audio features moments of high loudness.

(a) Test1_TrendOverQuestion
lowlevel.spectral_contrast_valleys.stdev.mean

(b) Comb_TrendOverQuestion
lowlevel.loudness_ebu128.momentary.mean

Figure 16: Distribution of feature data against ranking from the two most correlated features

Two brief observations are interesting. Firstly, that correlation coefficients for the ‘GrandAverage’ sets have on average slightly higher correlation coefficients than the ‘VersionAverage’ sets. This may be because there is less variation in the data, due to the repetition of the ranking, but it may also be taken as evidence the average ranking outlined above in Section 4.2.1 has a stronger relationship to the statistical data than the varying average rankings. Secondly, it is interesting that the simplified data set correlated no better (highest value: $r = .48$, $p = < .005$) than the standard 5 ranking version (highest value: $r = -0.5$, $p = < .005$).

4.4 Predictive Modelling in WEKA

The datasets were then loaded into the Weka platform where several predictive modelling routines were explored.

Previously, in Section 3.4, it was discussed that the task of modelling the responses could be approached both as a regression and a classification problem. Based on our assumptions about the rankings themselves; whether they are considered fixed and discrete, or continuous, simply integers on an infinitely divisible scale.

4.4.1 Regression Approach

A Simple Linear Regression (SLR) model and a Support Vector Machine Regression (SVMReg) model were the first to be tested. They were run with both the full feature set and with only the top five most correlated features. These were taken from the results of the Pearson correlation calculations. These runs were performed with a 10-fold cross-validation. The general correlation coefficients for each run can be seen in Figure 17.

Figure 17: Regression Modelling Results (correlation coefficient)

The first observation to make about the results is that the ‘GrandAverage’ datasets are modelled more successfully than their ‘VersionAverage’ counterparts, with the

exception of Test2 cases. In half of the cases the SLR with all 125 features, outperforms the SLR with only the top five features. The same is nearly true of the SVMReg, with the run using only the top five features outperforming those using the full feature set in only 4 out of 7 cases. Since the features are independent, therefore capturing different aspects of the problem, when combined they tend to improve the general performance. This would explain why the runs using the full feature set often outperform those using only the top five. However, the drawback of this is that these results are likely to suffer from overfitting.

Another clear observation is that the data sets of the individual tests (Test1 and Test2) perform far better than the combined sets. However, these are far less robust as they've been trained on half the data.

The simplified dataset also performs slightly poorer than the combined dataset, this result is compounded by the fact that the simplified has few degrees of freedom. So it should be modelled easier. This could be due to the fact that although Versions 'A' and 'D' are ranked 1st and 2nd on average, their high scoring maybe for different reasons. That is that the features of one are possibly not shared with the other. This would mean that giving them the same predictive output, actually makes it less clear exactly what the relationship is between the ranking and the statistics.

The second test was designed to be an extension of the first; simply to collect more data with slightly different parameterisation to account for some of the overfitting that might occur when modelling the first alone. Despite this, it was also of interest to us to use the separate tests datasets as training and testing sets. For this test, we use Test1 as the training set and Test2 as the testing set, as Test1 received more responses than Test2. Both the 'VersionAverage' sets and the 'GrandAverage sets were tested using both an SLR and a SVMReg. The 'VersionAverage' tests both scored very poorly. slightly better was the SLR run ($r = 0.216$, $p = < .005$) over the SMOReg run ($r = 0.149$, $p = < .005$). The scores were better across the board, but not by much, when the 'GrandAverage' was tested. The SLR proved to be more effective this time ($r = 0.357$, $p = < .005$), the SMOReg only scoring slightly better than random.

The fact that this cross-dataset validation yields worse results than simply using a single data set suggests that the models are incomplete, the models are learning different things about each dataset because they do not have enough data to properly model the problem.

4.4.2 Classification Approach

A classification approach was also explored as it would simplify the ‘to-be-predicted’ variable from continuous to discrete. It was hoped that this would improve the results.

	Multilayer Perceptron		Support Vector Machine	
	Full Feature Set	Top Five Features	Full Feature Set	Top Five Features
Test1_VersionAverage	0.237	0.086	0.2	?
Test1_GrandAverage	0.506	0.186	0.359	?
Test2_VersionAverage	0.541	?	?	?
Test2_GrandAverage	0.54	0.307	0.605	?
Comb_VersionAverage	0.249	0.142	0.215	?
Comb_GrandAverage	0.62	0.281	0.479	?
Comb_SimplifiedAverage	0.583	0.505	0.487	?

Figure 18: Classification results (f-measures)

To run classification models, the datasets had to be adapted slightly. The rankings, which were in the form of numeric values were changed to their written equivalent. Each dataset was run through a Multilayer Perceptron and a Support Vector Machine, once with the full feature set and once with the top five features, as was done in the regression approach. The results (f-measure) of the classification runs can be seen in Figure 18. The highest f-measure ($F_{1,6} = 0.605$, $p < .005$) was returned by ‘Test2_GrandAverage SMO (Full Set)’, the confusion matrix for which can be seen in Figure 19 (b), 61.90% of instances on that run were correctly classified. The poorest performing runs for which an f-measure was computed, the confusion matrix for which can be seen in Figure 19 (a), was ‘Test1_VersionAverage Multilayer Perceptron (Top Five Features)’ ($F_{1,6} = 0.086$, $p < .005$) (8% correctly classified instances). Along with ‘Test1_VersionAverage Multilayer Perceptron (Top Five Features)’, ‘Comb_VersionAverage Multilayer Perceptron (Top Five Features)’

($F_{1,6} = 0.142$, $p < .005$) (14.4% correctly classified instances) was the only other run to achieve a below ‘coin flip’ score, with accuracy worse than random.

In figure 18 it can be seen that there were no returned f-measures for the whole any of the SMO (Top Five Features) sets (this is denoted by the ‘?’ character). This is because they scored 0 for precision and/or recall, and thus because the f-measure is a weighted value of both, it is incalculable. To report the results of these tests we have included the confusion matrices for each of the seven runs in Figure 20 and the percentage of correctly classified instances in the following list. It is evident from this and Figure 18 that using just 5 features leads to a poorer performance on both types of classification model.

1. Comb_Simplified: 50%
2. Comb_VersionAverage: 32.60%
3. Comb_GrandAverage: 17.39%
4. Test1_VersionAverage: 4%
5. Test1_GrandAverage: 8%
6. Test2_VersionAverage: 52.38%
7. Test2_GrandAverage: 57.14%

```

a b c d e f  <-- classified as
0 0 0 3 0 1 | a = two
0 0 0 1 1 2 | b = three
0 0 0 0 1 2 | c = four
2 0 0 1 0 1 | d = one
0 0 2 0 1 2 | e = five
1 4 0 0 0 0 | f = zero

```

(a) Test1_VersionAverage Multilayer Perceptron (Top Five)

```

a b c d e f  <-- classified as
4 0 0 0 0 0 | a = two
0 3 0 1 0 0 | b = three
0 0 3 1 0 0 | c = five
0 2 1 0 0 0 | d = zero
0 0 2 0 1 0 | e = four
0 1 0 0 0 2 | f = one

```

(b) Test2_GrandAverage SMO (Full Set)

Figure 19: Confusion matrices displaying the range of results in classification accuracy

```

SimplifiedAverageSM06
a b c d <-- classified as
16 0 1 0 | a = one
8 0 0 0 | b = two
6 0 7 0 | c = three
8 0 0 0 | d = zero

```

(a) SimplifiedAverage

```

Comb_GrandAverageSM06          Comb_VersionAverageSM06
a b c d e f <-- classified as  a b c d e f <-- classified as
4 3 0 0 1 1 | a = two          0 0 0 5 0 1 | a = two
8 0 0 0 0 0 | b = three        0 0 0 4 1 1 | b = three
2 1 4 0 0 1 | c = five         0 0 0 2 3 0 | c = four
4 1 0 0 0 2 | d = one          0 0 0 6 1 2 | d = one
4 0 2 0 0 0 | e = four         0 0 0 3 9 0 | e = five
8 0 0 0 0 0 | f = zero        0 0 0 6 2 0 | f = zero

```

(b) Comb_GrandAverage

(c) Comb_VersionAverage

```

Test1_GrandAverageSM06        Test2_GrandAverageSM06
a b c d e f <-- classified as  a b c d e f <-- classified as
0 0 0 0 0 5 | a = two          2 1 0 0 1 0 | a = two
4 0 0 0 0 0 | b = three        0 4 0 0 0 0 | b = three
1 0 2 0 0 1 | c = five         0 0 4 0 0 0 | c = five
0 0 0 0 0 4 | d = one          1 2 0 0 0 0 | d = zero
2 0 0 0 0 1 | e = four         0 0 1 0 2 0 | e = four
5 0 0 0 0 0 | f = zero        0 1 2 0 0 0 | f = one

```

(d) Test1GrandAverage

(e) Test2_GrandAverage

```

Test1_VersionAverageSM06      Test2_VersionAverageSM06
a b c d e f <-- classified as  a b c d e f <-- classified as
0 0 0 2 1 1 | a = two          4 1 0 0 0 0 | a = one
0 0 0 0 0 4 | b = three        0 7 0 0 0 0 | b = five
0 0 0 0 1 2 | c = four         0 2 0 0 0 0 | c = three
0 0 0 0 0 4 | d = one          1 2 0 0 0 0 | d = zero
0 0 1 0 1 3 | e = five         0 2 0 0 0 0 | e = four
0 2 0 3 0 0 | f = zero        0 2 0 0 0 0 | f = two

```

(f) Test1_VersionAverage

(g) Test2_VersionAverage

Figure 20: Confusion matrices for SMO runs with only the top five features

4.5 Normalised Compression Distance results

The final analysis done on the results was to look at the Normalised Compression Distance (NCD) between each version and its reference track. NCD is a similarity metric based on the difference in compressibility between two files. A discussion on NCD can be found in 3.5. The results here were very significant. The peak correlation coefficient for NCD was higher than that of any of the Essentia statistics

($r = 0.64$, $p = < .001$), see Figure 21. It was also on average higher than any other, though it featured a high standard deviation and variance.

Because the NCD is in effect a similarity metric, its high correlation suggests that when subjects made the judgements they were ranking the version ‘most similar’ to the reference track. This is particularly interesting as the subjects never heard any of the reference tracks.

	Feature Name	Peak	Variance	Std Dev	Mean
1	NCD	0.636629245	0.005410412	0.0735555	0.512981796
2	tonal.hpcp_entropy.mean	0.590001201	0.004866098	0.069757421	0.448432823
3	lowlevel.loudness_ebu128.short_term.mean	-0.539671668	0.005784757	0.076057593	-0.448418923
4	tonal.hpcp_crest.mean	-0.586580209	0.003631798	0.0602644	-0.44760351
5	lowlevel.spectral_contrast_valleys.stdev.mean	0.62725575	0.01420318	0.119177095	0.433965583
6	lowlevel.loudness_ebu128.momentary.mean	-0.523980547	0.009724385	0.098612299	-0.408063576
7	tonal.hpcp.mean.mean	0.698511516	0.036330909	0.190606688	0.374443655
8	lowlevel.spectral_rms.stdev	0.482157644	0.004394627	0.066291984	0.372150076
9	tonal.hpcp.stdev.mean	0.487675389	0.008759027	0.093589671	0.356010621
10	tonal.hpcp.stdev.stdev	-0.537794919	0.013495335	0.116169425	-0.351232886

Figure 21: Most highly correlated features (ranking based on mean value)

4.6 Discussion

Due to the amount of data had at our disposal, we are limited in the scope of what can be commented on, and that which should be cautioned with reference to this. Not only were the responses to the listening tests limited but as was mentioned in Section 4.1.2, it was found that slightly over a quarter (26%) of the versions ranked had no consensus in their ranking. The 13 removed versions (and corresponding rankings) did not all have distributions as even as the one displayed in Figure 12 (b), some were found to have a bimodal distribution, where there was no consensus around a single value, but showed a dichotomic pattern; a distribution focus around two clear peaks. Since we wanted to take a single value for each of the versions an average had to be established; a midpoint between two peaks does not accurately represent the preferences expressed by the majority of the subjects and thus it was not used. As for why the items that appear to be “consensually difficult” were so, a content-based explanation is lacking. However, we found that the distribution of cases that were unclear to be skewed towards the front of the questionnaires. If the questionnaires were to be repeated, they should open with an attentive listening

exercise or even a dummy question. Furthermore, the question order should then be randomised.

Despite this, the rankings that we were left with proved to be statistically significant, not only this but the ‘GrandAverage’, the mode of the average rankings per question also proved to be statistically significant. Therefore we can say that the results we’ve obtained do point towards a degree of objectivity in the subjects preference for the versions that they were presented.

4.6.1 The ranking

Considering the average version rankings themselves, there are several assertions we can make about their order. The results of the average ranking were reported in full above in Section 4.2.1 and an explanation of the transformations themselves can be found in Section 3.1.1. To recap, however, the ranking was as follows:

1. Audio Compression
2. Band-pass filtering
3. Distortion
4. Transient Removal
5. Harmonic Randomisation

If we consider the top two and bottom two together we can say something about their commonalities. ‘Transient Removal’ and ‘Harmonic Randomisation’, making up the bottom two, are both arguably the closest of the transformations to a human ‘performance error’. ‘Harmonic Randomisation’, the scrambling of magnitude values in the frequency spectrum and thus degrading the pitch salience, has the perceived effect of making the performance sound ‘out of tune’. ‘Transient Removal’, either the blending or silencing of onsets and offsets, has the perceived effect of making the performance sounds ‘out of time’. At the other end of the ranking ‘Audio Compression’ and ‘Bandpassing’ make up the top two; these were the most preferred

items. Both of these transformations probably do not hold associations with human ‘performance error’, however conceivable they could hold associations with technology, sound projection and transmission. ‘Audio Compression’, is most commonly used as a production tool; a method of boosting the volume of the quieter moments relative to the loudest whilst also increasing the overall perceived loudness. The latter function was the core component of an arms race of loudness in ‘pop’ music over the previous several decades and thus it could be argued that the contemporary listener has ‘an ear for’ compressed music, it’s effect on what we’re used to hearing is rather normalised. ‘Band-pass filtering’, the attenuation of frequencies outside a given range, may hold an association with antiquated telecommunications technology which typically employed filters to reduce the amount of information that had to be transmitted to make speech intelligible. Again this has arguably had a normalising effect on our perception of frequency limited audio.

The two ranked lowest can be grouped by their perceptual association to human performance error, and the two ranked highest can be grouped by their perceptual association to audible effects of certain kinds technological transmission. Given this, we are then lead to ask if this correlation is causal? Could it be that the preference for ‘Audio Compression’ and ‘Band-pass filtering’ over ‘Transient Removal’ and ‘Harmonic Randomisation’ is due to these associations? If so, why?

If these associations are true and are affecting our judgements, what might the cause of this? They are both technological-aesthetic degradations, since either the technology involved itself or human interaction with the technology has a negative effect in the transmission of the aesthetic idea to the audience¹. The difference is that the degradation happens at different places in the process of artistic realisation. Degradation in performance occurs much closer to the artistic ideal than radio compression and band-pass filtering. Perhaps when we make these judgements we are aware of this.

Expanding on this idea, it is to view these technological mediations as filters. Pro-

¹The instruments or ensemble used in the performance of the composition are as much examples of music technology as the radio the compression plug-in. The guitar is a piece of music technology, as is the symphony orchestra.

posed early chapter in Section 2.9.1 was a way of thinking about these ‘filters’, as belonging to two different types of intersecting and overlapping aesthetic value that contributed to the whole: the ‘content aesthetic’ and the ‘container aesthetic’. We can say that the radio compression and band-pass filtering are located squarely in the ‘container aesthetic’ whereas the performance error lies somewhere between the ‘content aesthetic’ and the ‘container aesthetic’ depending on how the composition was conceived. Furthermore, nominally the ‘content’ is going to be far more affected by filters that fall under ‘content aesthetic’ than those that fall under ‘container aesthetic’. Thus perhaps the perceptive result of a degradation by a filter on the ‘container aesthetic’ will keep what the audience perceives as the compositional ideal nearly intact, whereas the opposite would be true of a filter on the ‘content aesthetic’. Colloquial evidence for this would be that a performance could be universally condemned - “*That cover band butchered one of my favourite band’s tracks!*”, whereas condemnation of a poor quality hi-fi or radio compression remains largely the purview of the audiophile, or ‘music snob’ - “*those speakers don’t do this track justice!*”

Distortion, ranked third, the median position, is also interesting when thought about in terms of ‘content’ and ‘container’ aesthetics. Distortion transects these the two as it can be used as a stylistic tool as well as a being introduced as an artefact during transmission.

Here then we can see a correlation between where and when, in terms of the production, transmission and projection of a composition, the associated degradation takes place on average, whether that’s close to the conception, in the case of performance, or at the point of projection, in the case of a band-limited speaker cone.

It is also possible that we are far more tolerant of technological inefficiencies or faults than human error. As if human error is always somehow avoidable and thus should be, whereas we somehow lack the vision to see how the machines could be improved. This has a compounding effect in that we become ‘familiar’ with technological faults.

4.6.2 Compressibility and the aesthetic experience

As was mentioned previously in Section 4.5, the NCD results correlation coefficient was found to be higher than any of the Essentia descriptors. NCD was explained in detail in Section 3.5, but briefly, NCD is a similarity metric based on the compressibility of the two items. If we relate this to the discussion in the previous section, we can say that NCD was found to be lowest when comparing the versions with associated degradations furthest from the point of initial artistic conception to the reference track, and furthest when comparing the versions with associated degradations nearest to the point of initial artistic conception to the reference track. This can be taken as evidence that the degradations made closer to the point of initial artistic conception affect the compressibility of the file to a greater degree than those made further from it.

This relates quite clearly to the work of Schidhuber[47, 2], Machado [1, 63, 66] and Hudson[25] who all relate the aesthetic experience to the successful neural encoding of artistic information, and define aesthetic value to be the ratio of complexity to compressibility. It appears that the versions we have created are increasing the complexity and decreasing the compressibility of the reference track to different degrees. Further, it appears that those with associated degradations closest to the point of initial artistic conception reduce the compressibility of the track the most. Our work here adds weight to the theory laid out by those authors.

Chapter 5

Conclusion

This thesis was motivated by what we found to be an oversight in the current approaches to computational aesthetics. Certain music or audio specific considerations had not been taken into account. Some of the current ambitions of the computational aesthetics of music- most notably measuring the aesthetic value of compositions relative to one another- require a more incremental approach. Here we attempted to tackle lack of consideration for the effects of technological mediation on the abstract conceptualisation of ‘the composition’. The goal of this research is therefore to explore the relationship between the aesthetic experience and the smallest aesthetic decisions, decisions which are beyond what is traditionally considered to be ‘artistic’

We tackled this by manually transforming an array of compositions, creating a series of ‘degraded’ versions for each. The transformations acted as exaggerated proxies for, or a reflection of, the effects of the technological mediation, transmission and/or speaker projection of these compositions. Via an online questionnaire, subjects were then asked to rank these transformations in terms of the aesthetic experience that they induced. These results were then analysed and combined with statistical information extracted from the audio presented. We used several predictive modelling techniques to explore the relationship between the features extracted from the audio and the rankings returned from the questionnaire.

We found that roughly 75% of the items that were presented to our participants to

be ranked were found to have a distribution that was unimodal. The rankings were also found to be statistically significant according to the results of the ANOVA test. The items whose ranking responses were unimodal were substituted for their mode averages. These averages also proved to be statistical significance. The averages represented each of the transformations presented to the subjects. There were five categories for each question. These were once again averaged to produce a ‘Grand Average’, that is, the overall average ranking for the versions across every questions. The ranking was as follows:

1. [Version D] Audio Compression
2. [Version A] Band-pass filtering
3. [Version B] Distortion
4. [Version E] Transient Removal
5. [Version C] Harmonic Randomisation

It was noted that the two highest-ranked versions were those most associated with a technological mediation, such as telephone, radio (in the case of Band-pass filtering) or an arguably overused audio tool (Audio Compression). In contrast, the two lowest-ranked version were those most associated with human performance error, such as mistuning (in the case of Harmonic Randomisation) and mis-timing (Transient Removal).

In calculating the Pearson Correlation coefficient, we found the following Essentia descriptors to be the most highly correlated.

1. ‘tonal.hpcp_entropy.mean’
2. ‘loudness_ebu128.momentary.mean’
3. ‘lowlevel.loudness_ebu128.momentary.mean’
4. ‘lowlevel.spectral_contrast_valleys.stdev.mean’

Since we received only 52 responses in our small study, any ML-based predictive modelling has to be considered to be largely speculative. Given this, we took the opportunity to explore the task of modelling the ranking as both a classification and a regression problem. We tested a Simple Linear Regression model and Support Vector Machine regression model on both the full data set, and on a smaller feature set of the most highly correlated individual descriptors. For the classification approach, a Multilayer Perceptron and a Support Vector Machine were used. The Classification approach generally found to be much less successful than the regression model.

Finally, the Normalised Compression Distance between each version and its (untransformed) reference was calculated. The Pearson correlation of this and the ranking was then also calculated. The coefficient of the NCD was higher in all groups than any of the individual Essentia statistics, peaking at $r = 0.64$, $p = < .001$. This is in line with the most compelling contemporary theories in computational aesthetics, such as those proposed by Machado and Cardoso[1] and Schmidhuber[2].

Our findings suggest that there is in fact a degree of objectivity in the way we make aesthetic judgements of audio at the ‘micro-level’. The results of the correlation coefficients between the NCD and the rankings contribute to the compression progress theory of aesthetic value. Our findings should inform the methods of any future research that aims to measure the aesthetic value of different compositions relative to one another. The stimuli presented are not abstract representations of ‘a composition’, but rather versions of ‘a composition’ where ‘non-artistic’ interventions will factor in on the aesthetic experience they induce.

5.1 Future Work

If this subject of research were to be pursued further¹, the following suggestions may indicate productive lines of enquiry. The whole work would naturally benefit

¹Reproducing this work should be quite straightforward if the plugins used to generate the versions can be found. If not, it wouldn’t devalue the work if a different plugin was used to achieve the same results. The code snippets used to extract the Essentia descriptors, to calculate the Pearson correlations and to calculate the NCD can be found on the following GitHub repository: <https://github.com/martindisley/Masters-Thesis-Exploring-Objectivity-in-the-Aesthetic-Experience-of-Audio-Quality>

from the collection of further data. The more the questionnaire could be repeated with new stimuli (i.e. new compositions and versions made using the same methods outline here) the more robust the results would be.

If the experiment were to be taken further, it would be interesting to varying not just the style of the degradations presented but also their intensity, or ‘severity’. Doing so would likely end up with a more robust ranking. For instance, if both Version A (severity level 1) and Version A (severity level 2) were ranked below both intensity levels of Version B, then we could more robustly argue that Version A is considered to be worse than Version B.

Although not necessarily a continuation of the work done here, the most fruitful avenue of work in the field of computational aesthetics is arguably in developing a better proxy for neural encoding. It would be our recommendation to start with an exploration of the possibility of fractal density based compression for audio, which has been fruitful in the visual arts[49, 66, 67]. There is some existing work using fractal dimensions in audio for speaker identification[68] and for Indian musical instrument recognition[69].

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